

Studies on Infrared Spectra of some Azalactones

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Infrared spectra of some 4-(*p*-substituted-benzylidene)-2-phenyl-5-oxazolones have been studied with reference to frequency of C=N and C=O groups of the ring, which were not significantly influenced by variations of the *para*-substituent.

AZLACTONES are important as intermediates in the synthesis of amino acids, arylacetic acid and many natural products. Uv absorptions spectra of azlactones have been studied by number of workers^{1,2}. Infrared absorptions curves for 4-(*p*-methoxybenzyl)-2-phenyl-5-oxazolones have also been reported³. The purpose of the present work is to determine the infrared absorption spectra of some 4-(*p*-substituted-benzylidene)-2-phenyl-5-oxa-

zolones and to study the effect of the *para*-substituent of the phenyl ring (Ar) in the normal absorptions of C=O and C=N of the oxazolone ring. No ir data appear to have been reported on any of the compounds studied in the present work.

Results and Discussion

Examination of the ir spectra of the oxazolones studied shows that these have marked similarity, leaving for the case of special group absorptions, such as 782 for C-Cl in halogen-substituted,

1 350 for C-NO₂ in intro-substituted, 1 455 and 1 475 for C-H deformation in methoxy-substituted and 1 457 cm⁻¹ for O-CH₂-O in methylenedioxy-substituted compound.

All compounds studied showed characteristic strong absorptions at 700, 875 and 1 175 cm⁻¹. The latter is due to lactonic C-O stretch which is practically uninfluenced by the *para*-substituent in the phenyl ring (Ar). In all the compounds studied the absorptions due to C=O and C=N stretch appeared in the regions 1 788-1 810 and 1 655-1 670 cm⁻¹, respectively, which are not much different from the respective normal values of 1 807 and 1 667 cm⁻¹ observed for benzaldehyde azalactone (Table 1).

Experimental

The azlactones were prepared according to the standard procedure⁴ by reacting hippuric acid (1 mol) and acetic anhydride (2 mol) with aromatic aldehydes (1 mol) in presence of sodium acetate (1 mol). Ir spectra were determined in KBr disc using a Unicam SP 1000 spectrophotometer. The results are shown in the tabular form showing the principal absorptions.

TABLE 1—IR SPECTRAL BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	Ar	Molecular formula	M.p. ^a °C	$\nu_{C=O}$	$\nu_{C=N}$	ν_{C-O}	$\nu_{C=C}$
1.	Phenyl	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ N	166	1 807	1 667	1 175	1 570
2.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₃ N	109	1 807	1 670	1 177	1 577
3.	4-Methoxyphenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₃ N	160	1 800	1 668	1 177	1 585
4.	3,4-Methylene-dioxyphenyl	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₄ N	195	1 788	1 657	1 177	1 560
5.	4-Chlorophenyl	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₂ NCl	205	1 810	1 667	1 175	1 570
6.	4-Dimethyl-aminophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂	214	1 795	1 665	1 180	1 550
7.	2-Methoxy-5,6-benzophenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₃ N	177	1 807	1 670	1 182	1 575
8.	4-Nitrophenyl	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂	234	1 807	1 665	1 175	1 565
9.	Cinnamyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ O ₂ N	140	1 795	1 655	1 175	1 580

* Crystallised from ethanol into shiny yellow or yellow crystals.

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